

TEACHING COMMUNICATION IN KARAKALPAK LANGUAGE IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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***Abstract.** The article is devoted to a problem of formation of skills of communication of children in the karakalpak language on the basis of principle of succession and continuity of education. In the article open necessity of development of theoretical and methodical bases of training to the second language with a support on national ideology of independence, activization speech and intellectual, activization speech and intellectual of activity of children, familiarizing them to spiritual values of the karakalpak people.*

***Keywords:** problem, formation, skill, communication, karakalpak language, base, principle, succession, continuity, education.*

At the present stage of the formation of sovereign republics, the growth of national self-consciousness, the revival of interest in the past people, its richest spiritual heritage, the problem of taking into account national pedagogical traditions is actualized, including the problem of spirituality and morality in the process of forming communication skills in the Karakalpak language among children of non-indigenous nationality in the system continuous education. In Karakalpakstan, centuries-old traditions of education based on direct communication, high spirituality and morality have been practically lost.

In the context of the implementation of the national model of personnel training, the fundamental factors in teaching the younger generation the state (Karakalpak) language is taking into account the lifestyle of the Karakalpak people, the specifics of natural and social conditions, customs and traditions, based on a rich historical and spiritual heritage, world practice and the positive experience of the best teachers.

The system of continuous education in the process of developing communication skills in the Karakalpak language among the younger generation provides for the creation of the necessary conditions for the development of a spiritually rich, socially active person who is able to freely communicate in the state language in various spheres of life (political, environmental, social and cultural).

Of essential importance in the assimilation of the Karakalpak language by Russian-speaking children is the implementation of such important didactic principles: practical and communicative orientation, scientific character, historicism, consistency, connection with life, systematicity, repetition with a gradual complication of tasks, optimization of the load, consciousness and activity of students, continuity and consistency in content, forms of organization of work, methods and techniques, between the levels of the education system, taking into account age characteristics, taking into account the level of preparedness of children, reflecting national characteristics, generalizing educational material (generalization, logical

transition from the particular to the general, subordination of particular phenomena to a general principle).

Particular attention deserves the question of the reasons for success and failure in the assimilation of the Karakalpak language by students in classes with the Russian language of instruction. This can include not only differences in the phonetic, lexical, grammatical systems of the Russian and Karakalpak languages, but also a number of other reasons that affect the course and results of the didactic process, called factors in modern pedagogy.

Thus, each teacher must first of all establish the reasons for the decrease in students' interest in learning the language, which is an important reason for the decrease in the quality of knowledge.

The formation of communication skills in the Karakalpak language means not just learning to speak, but solving various communication tasks in real life situations.

The communicative orientation of learning involves mastering the ability to plan one's speech behavior, correlating the goals of each speech act with the expression of content and available foreign language means, and using speech etiquette. Mediated communication (through a book) makes it possible to develop the ability to navigate the text, understand the author's intention, and practically evaluate the content of what is read.

The communicative orientation of teaching the Karakalpak language is realized in the process of solving particular problems, according to which students must master a certain active and passive vocabulary, acquire orthoepic, grammatical, word-formation, stylistic, spelling and, above all, communicative and speech skills and abilities.

Teaching the Karakalpak language also includes educational and developmental needs for self-education, the development of skills and abilities for independent work with a book in the Karakalpak language, the ability to use reference literature, dictionaries, read thoughtfully, systematize material, and draw conclusions. Lessons of the Karakalpak language should contribute to the formation of skills for rational independent work, a culture of mental work.

The content of the lessons of the Karakalpak language, speech situations, themes of the Karakalpak speech, textual material and the system of tasks for it should help in the formation of the national self-consciousness of students, take into account and reflect in a reasonable ratio the specifics of advanced national traditions and cultures.

Since education and upbringing are specific forms of social activity, pedagogical laws also retain the specifics of the laws of social development.

When teaching the Karakalpak language, children can, and the educator should help them acquire basic skills to use the language being studied for communication.

The oral beginning from the first steps creates the conditions for revealing the communicative function of the language and allows you to bring the learning process closer to the conditions of real communication, which arouses students' interest in the subject and creates a fairly high motivation to learn the Karakalpak language.

In accordance with the requirements of teaching scientists, education, knowledge, skills and abilities should be the results of the intended goal - the formation of communication skills based on the selection of the most significant educational content, means, ensuring the development of interest in the language and the use of such methods and techniques, which would contribute to the activation of the mental and speech activity of preschoolers and schoolchildren, providing consciousness and strength in the assimilation of knowledge.

At the same time, scientists consider it especially important to observe the inseparable unity of education, upbringing and development of students, the formation of a socially active personality, showing the need for new knowledge to use it in communication with others.

The priority of the state language in the conditions of bilingualism presupposes a distinction between the native and the studied language, determines the differentiation of learning goals from the needs of students in communication, without lowering the level of the state standard of education.

Teaching the Karakalpak language to children means the formation of the ability to solve communication problems in the field of communication, which requires search work in improving the organization of the form of work with children, the use of effective methods and techniques for teaching the formation of communication skills in order to accelerate the process of mastering children's spoken language.

One of the effective ways to increase the activity of children, develop their thinking, improve the quality of children's knowledge is the formation of communication skills and the systematic use of games. Games provide simultaneously educational, developing and educational functions of the learning process.

The use of situational games allows you to increase the number of exercises, significantly diversify the nature of situational and problem situations, ensure the growth of children's creative activity; contributes to the emergence and development of the creative interests of students.

The modern requirements for the training of national personnel in the Republics of Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan focus on the comprehensive development of the personality of the trainees, an important component of which is the language culture, literate knowledge of the native and the number of which the Karakalpak language is also becoming a means of communication and mutual enrichment. Language training includes, first of all, the development of strong skills and abilities in correct pronunciation, vocabulary, grammar and coherent speech, the basic structure of which is the formation of communication skills.

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